

Spectrophotometric and Electrometric Investigations on the Composition and Stability of Silicomolybdic Acid

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Silicic and molybdic acids, both prepared by using ion-exchange resin, are found to interact with each other, yielding a yellow complex acid having Si to Mo ratio as 1 : 8. The complex acid, so formed, is found to have a strength intermediate between that of the parent acids. The formation of the 1 : 8 complex depends on the initial concentrations of the components and temperature and has got a maximum absorption at 310 m μ . Its composition has been determined by applying Job's method of continued variations, adopting spectrophotometric and pH-metric data. An explanation of the variation of conductance of the Job's mixtures at first linearly upto 1 : 3 ratio of Si to Mo and thereafter nonlinearly is offered.

In recent years, evidences¹⁻² for the existence of a number of complex acids of Si and Mo have been obtained. The 8- and 12-silico-molybdic acids (the ratio of Si: Mo as 1: 8 and 1:12) are reported³⁻⁴ to exist in the pH range of 1.2 to 4.6. Using suitable salts of the two acids and also by adding mineral acids to adjust pH investigations⁵⁻⁷ have been carried out for the absorption spectra, rate of formation, colour dependence on temperature etc. of 8 and 12 complex acids of Si and Mo. In the present investigation, silicic and molybdic acids, prepared by using ion-exchange method, have been used to study the composition and some other characteristics of the pure silico-molybdic acid formed under conditions of the experiment.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the experiments were carried out at 25°. The reagents used were all A.R. quality. Sodium molybdate was of E. Merck and sodium silicate was of Reidel D. Haen. HCl used was of International Chemical Industries (India). The resin was a cation exchanger [Amberlite I.R.—120 (H)] of Rohm and Haas Company, Pennsylvania. All spectrophotometric measurements were taken in a Beckman spectrophotometer (Model DU) using cuvettes of path length 1 cm. For pH and conductance measurements, a Cambridge Universal bench type pH-meter and a Philips conductivity bridge (PR 500 model) operating in the most sensitive range at 1000 C/S. were used.

Both the acids were prepared in a manner described previously⁸ by percolating through two long separate columns (each 20 cm in length and made of Pyrex glass) packed

1. Ripman and Kim, *Acad. rep. Populaire Romina, Filiala Olaj, studii cercetari Chim.* 1957, 3, 21.
2. Ripman et al., *Naturwiss.*, 1957, 44, 421; *Bull. Soc. Chim.* 1958, 1507.
3. Kamula and Rosolowsky, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1960, 34, 8.
4. Kamula and Wolfrain, *Chem. Anal.* Warsaw, 1958, 3, 593.
5. Chanven et al., *Bull. Soc. Chim.* 1959, 1100.
6. Skerlak, *Bull. Soc. Chim. rep. Populaire, Boivin et Herzogovine*, 1956, 5, 27.
7. Tarutani, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1956, 77, 743.
8. Mullick et al., *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 197.

with the resin on a glass wool (E. Merck) bed at the bottom. Silicic acid was estimated by evaporating a known volume in a porcelain crucible, ignited and weighed as SiO_2 . Molybdic acid was estimated both gravimetrically and volumetrically by adding excess of sodium hydroxide and titrating the excess alkali with standard succinic acid after keeping the mixture for 24 hr. Both the methods provided concurrent result but for easy experimental manipulation, the volumetric method was adopted.

DISCUSSION

Absorption Maximum of the Complex

Neither silicic nor molybdic acid yielded a maximum at any wave length of light as is evident from the curves 1, 2 and 3 of Fig. 1 for 0.02 *M* silicic and 0.001 *M* and 0.02*M* molybdic acid. For the same concentration of both the acids, the optical density in the case of molybdic acid was higher than that of silicic acid. With water as control, the absorption spectrum of not a single mixture of the two acids was also maximum (vide, curve 4, Fig. 1). The only difference that the optical density for any ratio of Si and Mo is greater than the corresponding individual acids is suggestive of a complex formation. When, however, a blank containing the same concentration of molybdic acid for a particular ratio of Si and Mo was used, the plot of O.D. difference between the ratio and the corresponding molybdic acid control against wave lengths resulted a distinct maximum at 310 μ as shown in Fig. 2. Curves 1, 2 and 3 of Fig. 3 illustrate this for 1:8, 1:7 and 1:11 ratio as Si: Mo at a total concentration of 0.001 (*M*). The concentration of silicic acid for such mixtures was so low compared to molybdic acid that its absorption could reasonably be neglected.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Composition of the Complex

(i) *From absorption Measurement.*—For the elucidation of the composition of the complex, Job's⁹ method of continued variations was employed. Several mixtures of silicic and molybdic acids having ratios ranging from 4:1 to 1:14 as Si: Mo were made at differ-

9. Job *Compt. rend.*, 1928, 180, 928.

ent molecular concentrations starting from 0.04 *M* to 0.001 *M*. These were allowed to keep for a long time to attain equilibrium. Occasional measurement of optical density

λ in mμ
FIG. 3

both in the visible and also in the ultraviolet regions, wherever necessary, was carried out and the constant value of O.D. for each sample ensured as the state of complete reaction. The plot of O.D. values against the corresponding mole fractions of molybdic acid are exemplified in Fig. 4 and 5, respectively. For each individual curve, maximum corresponds to 1:8 silico-molybdic acid in solution over a concentration range of 0.001 (*M*) to 0.04 (*M*). In figure 4, some data in the cases of 0.04 (*M*) and 0.03 (*M*) acids are shown starting from the period of initial mixing upto the final stage of complete reaction (vide curves 1' and 2').

Molefraction of Molybdic Acid
FIG. 4

Molefraction of Molybdic Acid
FIG. 5

(ii) *From pH Measurement.*—The pH of the silicic and molybdic acids at equimolar concentration was found to differ considerably. For 0.04 *M* concentration, the pH of the

former acid was 3.03 and that of the latter was 1.99. It was observed from a careful measurement of pH of the Job mixtures that with the increase of molybdic acid ratio, pH values decreased gradually by at 1:8 ratio; the value, however, increased suddenly, falling again in the subsequent mixtures. Conclusion could, therefore, be drawn about the formation of a 1:8 silico-molybdic of strength $>$ silicic acid but $<$ molybdic acid. In Fig. 6 the variation of pH against the molar ratio of molybdic acid is shown.

FIG. 6

(iii) *From conductance Measurement.*—It is evident from Fig. 7 that the plot of conductance of the mixtures of silicic and molybdic acids against the mole fraction of molybdic acid yields two breaks corresponding to the ratio of Si and Mo as 1:3 and 1:8 respectively. But as both pH and spectrophotometric measurements indicate the composition of a 1:8 complex, the aforesaid observation can be explained in the following plausible manner.

In the mixture of silicic and molybdic acids there exist unreacted silicic and molybdic acids and also the complex acid.

Let,

$$M_s = \frac{\text{Si}}{\text{Si} + \text{Mo}} = \text{molefraction of silicic acid.}$$

$$M_m = \frac{\text{Mo}}{\text{Si} + \text{Mo}} = \text{,, ,, molybdic acid.}$$

Total concentration of each mixture = C_T (constant for a particular Job set).

Therefore concentration of free molybdic acid = C_{mf} .

(i) Concentration of the complex = $(M_m \cdot C_T - C_{mf})/8$ (since 8 molecules of molybdic acid are present in 1 mole of the complex).

(ii) Concentration of free silicic acid = $\{M_s C_T - (M_m C_T - C_{mf})/8\}$ ($\therefore$ concentration of silicic acid reacted).

Now assuming the conductance of each individual species being proportional to the number of moles, i.e. the concentration, the sum total conductance is given by

FIG. 7

$$S = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 = K_1 [M_s C_T - (M_m C_T - C_{mf})/8] + K_2 (M_m C_T - C_{mf})/8 + K_3 C_{mf} \quad \dots (1)$$

In this relation suffixes 1, 2 and 3 of S and K represent the respective conductance and proportionality constants of free silicic, complex and free molybdic acid, respectively. On rearranging, equation (1) becomes

$$S = K_1 M_s C_T + \frac{(K_2 - K_1)}{8} M_m C_T + \left(\frac{K_1}{8} - \frac{K_2}{8} + K_3 \right) C_{mf} \quad \dots (2)$$

Again, assume that upto the ratios of Si : Mo in the mixture in which molybdic acid is not appreciable in regards that one of its molecules consumes 1/8 part of a silicic acid molecule, the concentration of the unconsumed molybdic acid is negligible and hence the last term of equation (2) can reasonably be neglected.

Therefore, the final form of equation (2) becomes,

$$S = K_1 M_s C_T + C_T \left(\frac{K_2 - K_1}{8} \right) M_m \quad \dots (3)$$

$$= K_1 C_T (1 - M_m) + C_T \left(\frac{K_2 - K_1}{8} \right) M_m \quad \dots (4)$$

or

$$S = K_1 C_T + C_T \left(\frac{K_2 - \theta K_1}{8} \right) M_m \quad \dots (5)$$

Therefore, a plot of S (specific conductance) against M_m (mole fraction of molybdic acid) will yield a straight line. At a ratio of 1:4 of Si to Mo (half of the ideal complex-forming ratio, i.e. 1:8) the amount of free molybdic acid present has got a definite and accountable contribution on the total conductance of the solution. In that case, equation (2) will be applicable and the linearity will necessarily not be maintained. In the case of 0.04 M concentration, the effect is obviously more prominent than that of 0.03 M concentration.

As the concentration of silicic acid falls rapidly in proceeding ratio from 1:4, its conductance participating function is appreciably slow. Therefore the slow increase in the amount of the complex, having comparatively small conductance with respect to the molybdic acid, and the accountable amount of the free molybdic acid though drag up the conductance to higher values, yet the obvious downwards curving tendency is observed. But as soon as the ideal ratio (1:8) is exceeded, the only free molybdic acid in considerable excess causes the shooting up of the curve. In the case of pH measurement, only one inflection at 1:8 ratio was obtained. This is reasonable because the accountable, though little, amount of free molybdic acid, which causes another inflection after 1:3 ratio prior to 1:8, will have prominent effect on the total conductance of the solution. But a little excess in molybdic acid, i.e. a little excess in hydrogen ion concentration, will have but little effect on the pH values. The conductance measurements were performed at two different total mixture concentrations and at a constant temperature (25°) the slope ratio of the two sets according to the equation (5) should be equal to the ratio of their concentration. So,

$$\frac{(K_a - 9K_1)}{8} C_{T_1} : \frac{(K_a - 9K_1)}{8} C_{T_2} = (\text{slope})_1 : (\text{slope})_2$$

or

$$\frac{C_{T_1}}{C_{T_2}} = \frac{(\text{Slope})_1}{(\text{slope})_2}$$

or

$$\frac{0.04M}{0.03M} = \frac{3.175 \times 10^{-3}}{2.775 \times 10^{-3}}$$

This close analogy between the two values (1.33 and 1.32), thus obtained, justifies the applicability of equation (5) mentioned above. When the values of the intercepts are divided by their respective concentrations, the values of K_1 are found to be 11.5×10^{-3} and 11.33×10^{-3} . The experimentally determined values of the conductance of silicic acid at the above mentioned concentrations were found to correspond also to those obtained by multiplying the concentration by the average of K_1 values i.e. 11.47×10^{-3} .

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration

The variation in hydrogen-ion concentration on the stability of the complex was studied either by adding HCl or by diluting a more concentrated complex acid to less unsettled value. Only spectrophotometric studies in the ultraviolet region were undertaken in the elucidation as being the most prominent and distinctive feature of the complex. In all cases molybdic acid blanks, having the same concentrations as present in the complex and under identical H^+ -ion concentrations, were used. The sample having 1:8 ratio of Si: Mo was diluted to concentrations 0.001 M and lower values and their

spectra were taken immediately after dilution as also after allowing them considerable time. The values obtained are shown in Fig. 8; curves 1, 2 and 3 represent the spectra of the complex in presence of 1*N* and 0.5*N* HCl and in absence of HCl and immediately after dilution. Peaks were obtained always at 310 $m\mu$, suggestive of the existence of the 1:8 complex at these acid concentrations. The higher values of O.D. of the left arm of the Maxwellian curve than that of non-added HCl curve may be ascribed to the decrease of absorption capacity due to some polymerisation of the molybdic acid blanks at the higher acid concentrations, thus rendering the difference (i.e. of the complex mixture that of molybdic acid blank) greater in the range of wave lengths starting from 310 $m\mu$ and backwards. Curve 4 represents the spectrum for complex in water at 0.0005*M* immediately

after mixing. It forms a peak at 310 $m\mu$, but the value of the O.D at maximum being half of that obtained in the case of double concentration (0.001M) suggests the zero loss of any complex due to dilution at that concentration. It had shown another maximum at 249 $m\mu$ which could not be reached in the case of double strength as being out of the slit adjusting capacity of the spectrophotometer at an equal concentration of molybdic acid as blank. Curves 5 and 6 represent absorption spectra of the complex at 0.0005M in 0.5N-HCl and water respectively, but after seven days from the time of mixing. Though in these cases also the maximum is at 310 $m\mu$, the absorption at each wave length for case 5 is always less than that of case 6, suggesting thereby that in presence of acid the complex decomposes appreciably with time. The O.D of curve 6 is again less than that of curve 4. So, it may be concluded that dilution with water or with acid decomposes the complex to certain extent with time. The limit of pH in which the complex was found to exhibit its molecular composition is 0.30—6.26.

The formation of the so far discussed 8-silico-molybdic acid may be ascribed to the reaction of two fourfold condensed polymolybdic acid units¹⁰ with one monosilicic acid molecule. Thus,

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